

Research Article

Development and validation of reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography method for simultaneous estimation of Nebivolol HCl and Cilnidipine in combined tablet dosage form

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ABSTRACT

Objective: A simple, precise and accurate reversed phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method has been developed and subsequently validated for the simultaneous estimation of Nebivolol HCl and Cilnidipine in tablet formulation.

Methods: The adequate separation was carried out using Grace Smart C18 column (250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m particle size), mixture of 0.05 M Potassium dihydrogen phosphate PH 5.0 and Methanol 30:70 % v/v as a mobile phase with a flow rate of 1 ml/min and the effluent was monitored at 225 nm using PDA detector. The retention time of Nebivolol HCl and Cilnidipine were 4.057 min and 6.470 min respectively.

Results: Linearity for Nebivolol HCl and Cilnidipine were found in the range of 5-15 μ g/ml and 10-30 μ g/ml ($R^2 = 0.998$) respectively. The accuracy of the present method was evaluated at 80%, 100% and 120%. The % recoveries of both drugs were found to be in range of 99.698-100.108% and 99.497-99.512% for Nebivolol HCl and Cilnidipine respectively. Precision studies were carried out and the RSD values were less than two. The method was found to be robust.

Conclusions: The proposed method was found to be specific, accurate, precise and robust can be used for simultaneous estimation of these drugs in tablet dosage form.

Keywords: Nebivolol HCl, Cilnidipine, Reversed-phase HPLC, Validation

Introduction

Nebivolol HCl (NEB) is designated chemically as 1-(6-Fluorochroman-2-yl) - {[2- (6-fluorochroman-2-yl)-2-hydroxyethyl] amino}-ethanol (Figure 1), represents the class of Benzopyrans, β_1 receptor blocker with nitric oxide potentiating

vasodilatory effect used in treatment of hypertension.¹ NEB lowering the heart rate and blood pressure and also prevent the release of renin, which is a hormone produced by the kidney may also bind beta 2 receptors.^{2,3} Various analytical methods have been reported for the estimation of NEB as alone as well as in

combination with other drugs. They include spectrophotometric methods^{4,5}, HPLC^{6,7}, TLC⁸, stability indicating HPLC methods with Valsartan⁹, Amlodipine Basylate¹⁰.

Figure 1: Chemical Structure of NEB.

Cilnidipine (CIL) is designated chemically as 3-(E)-3-Phenyl-2-propenyl,5-2-methoxyethyl-2,6-dimethyl-4-(m-nitrophenyl)-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate (Figure 2), represents the class of calcium channel blocker. It inhibits cellular influx of calcium, consequently causing vasodilatation and used in the drug therapy of hypertension.^{11,12} Various analytical methods have been reported for the estimation of CIL as alone as well as in combination with other drugs. They include spectrophotometric methods¹³, LC-MS¹⁴, HPLC-MS/MS¹⁵ and HPTLC¹⁶ methods.

Figure 2: Chemical structure of CIL.

However, an extensive literature search didn't reveal any estimation method for both the drugs in their combined dosage form. Therefore, attempt was made to develop and validate simple, precise, and accurate reversed phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for simultaneous determination of both the drugs in their combined dosage form.

Materials and Methods

Apparatus

Young lin HPLC system was used for method development and validation. Data acquisition

was performed on YL 9100 HPLC software. The separation were achieved on Grace Smart C₁₈ (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) column. Digital balance (Sartorius CP224S, Sensitivity: 0.1 mg), Ultrasonic cleaner (PCi, 1.5L, 5H), pH meter (Systonic) and Pipettes and volumetric flask (Borosil) used during study.

Reagents and materials

NEB and CIL were obtained as gift samples from Eris Life sciences, Ahmedabad. NEB and CIL combined dosage form tablets were purchased from local market. HPLC grade Acetonitrile, Water and Hydrochloric acid, Methanol and Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate of analytical grade were obtained from SD Fine Chem Ltd.

Chromatographic conditions

The column was maintained at room temperature and the eluent was monitored at 225 nm using PDA detector. The mixture of 0.05M Potassium dihydrogen phosphate PH 5.0 and Methanol in proportion of 30:70 % v/v at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min was used as a mobile phase. The injection volume was 20μl.

Preparation of stock solution (NEB 100 μg/ml and CIL 200 μg/ml)

An accurately weighed quantity of standard NEB (10 mg) and CIL (20 mg) Were transferred to 100 ml volumetric flasks and volumes were made up to mark with mobile phase to get 100 μg/ml of NEB and 200 μg/ml of CIL.

Preparation of mobile phase: (0.05 M KH₂PO₄ pH-5 Adjusted with 0.1 N NaOH : Methanol (30:70 %V/V)

An accurately weighed 0.68 gm of potassium dihydrogenate phosphate (0.1M) was transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask, followed by addition of 95 ml HPLC grade water, pH 5 was adjusted with 0.1 N NaOH, volume was made up to mark with HPLC grade water. Above solution filtered with vacuum filter using filter membrane. 30 ml of buffer and 70 ml Methanol was mixed and solution was sonicated for degassing.

NEB and CIL standard stock solutions

For HPLC analysis 10 mg of NEB and 20 mg CIL powder was weighed accurately using Sartorius CP224S Digital balance and transferred in to 100 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with mobile phase to produce stock solution containing 100 µg/ml of NEB and 200 µg/ml CIL respectively.

NEB and CIL sample stock solution

20 tablets were weighed accurately and powdered. A quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg NEB and 20 mg of CIL was weighed accurately and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. Added 60 ml mobile phase and sonicated for 30 min and made up volume with mobile phase to produce a test solution having 100 µg/ml NEB and 200 µg/ml CIL and filtered through a Whatman Filter Paper no. 42. The resulted test solution was then analyzed for assay determination.

System suitability parameters

System suitability tests were performed to verify that the resolution and repeatability of the system were adequate for the analysis intended. The parameters monitored for system suitability includes retention time, theoretical plate number, peak area, tailing factor and resolution. The repeatability of these parameters was checked by injecting three times the test solution of 10 µg/ml NEB and 20 µg/ml CIL. The results shown in Table 1 were within acceptable limits.

Method validation

Specificity

Specificity of method can be termed as absence of any interference at retention times of samples. Specificity was performed by injecting blank and standard preparations. Chromatograms were recorded and retention times from sample and standard preparations were compared for identification of analytes.

Calibration curve (Linearity)

A series of standard solutions 5-15 µg/ml of NEB and 10-30 µg/ml of CIL were prepared. An

aliquot of 20 µl of each solution was injected 3 times for each standard solutions and peak area was observed. Plot of average peak area versus the concentration is plotted and from this the correlation coefficient and regression equation were generated. The calibration data of NEB and CIL is given in Table 3, while Figure 4 and 5 represent linearity graphs of both drugs respectively.

Accuracy (% Recovery)

Accuracy was determined by calculating recovery of NEB and CIL by the standard addition method. Known amounts of standard solutions of NEB (4, 5 and 6 µg/ml) and CIL (8, 10 and 12 µg/ml) were added to a pre quantified test solutions of NEB (10 µg/ml) and CIL (20 µg/ml). Each solution was injected in triplicate and the recovery was calculated by measuring peak areas. Results are shown in Table 4.

Method precision

The method was validated in terms of intra-day inter-day precision. The solution containing 10µg/ml of NEB and 20 µg/ml of CIL was injected six times for repeatability study. Inter-day and intra-day study was performed by injecting 50, 10 and 15 µg/ml of NEB and 10, 20 and 30 µg/ml of CIL solutions three times for each aliquots. The %RSD for precision study was found less than 2% as shown in Table 5.

Limit of detection and limit of quantification

The limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantification (LOQ) of the drug were derived by calculating the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N, i.e., 3.3 for LOD and 10 for LOQ) using the following equations as per International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma/S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma/S$$

Where σ = the standard deviation of the response and S = Slope of calibration curve.

Robustness

Robustness was carried by varying three parameters from the optimized chromatographic conditions. No significant change was observed.

Analysis NEB and CIL in combined dosage forms

Pharmaceutical formulation of NEB and CIL in combined dosage form was purchased from local pharmacy. The response of combined dosage form was measured at 225 nm for quantification of NEB and CIL by using RP-HPLC. The amounts of NEB and CIL present in sample solution were determined by the responses into the regression equation for NEB and CIL in the method. Results are given in Table 7.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Results for system suitability parameters.

Parameters	NEB (mean ± SD)*	CIL (mean ± SD)*
Retention time (min)	4.056 ± 0.001	6.471 ± 0.002
Theoretical plate	7096.667 ± 1.527	7155.33 ± 1.527
Tailing factor	1.384 ± 0.001	1.355 ± 0.003
Resolution	9.772 ± 0.008	

* = average of three determinations, SD=Standard deviation

To optimize the RP-HPLC parameters, several mobile phase compositions were tried. A satisfactory separation and good peak symmetry was found in a mixture of 0.05M Potassium dihydrogen phosphate PH 5.0 and Methanol 30:70 % v/v and 1.0 ml/min flow rate proved to be better than the other mixtures in terms of resolution and peak shape. The effluent was monitored at 225 nm using PDA detector. As it was shown in Figure 3 the retention time of NEB and CIL were 4.057 min and 6.470 min respectively. The method was validated in terms of linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity,

limit of detection and limit of quantification. Linearity of NEB and CIL were in the range of 5-10 µg/ml and 10-30 µg/ml respectively. The proposed method enables rapid quantification and simultaneous analysis of both drugs for commercial formulations without any excipients interference. The method can be used for routine analysis of marketed products of NEB and CIL in combined tablet formulation. System suitability test parameters for NEB and CIL for the RP-HPLC method are reported in Table 1. The optical and regression characteristics and validation parameters are reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Optical and regression characteristics and validation parameters of HPLC method for analysis of NEBI and CIL.

Parameter	Nebivolol HCl	Cilnidipine
Calibration Range	5-15 µg/ml	10-30 µg/ml
Regression Equation	Y= 118.2x + 11.91	Y=117.9x + 48.85
Slope (m)	118.2	117.9
Intercept (c)	11.91	48.85
Correlation co-efficient (R ²)	0.998	0.998
Inter Day (%RSD)	0.389-1.020	0.304-0.802
Intra Day (%RSD)	0.452-0.715	0.490-1.084
Repeatability (%RSD)	0.541	0.802
Detection Limit (µg/ml)	0.494 µg/ml	0.992 µg/ml
Quantitation Limit (µg/ml)	1.496 µg/ml	3.006 µg/ml

Figure 3: Optimised condition chromatogram of NEB (10 µg/ml) and CIL (20 µg/ml).

Table 3: Linearity study data for NEB and CIL.

S r N o	Nebivolol HCl			Cilnidipine		
	Conc (µg/ml)	Avg. area *	%RSD	Conc (µg/ml)	Avg. area *	%RSD
1	5	608.172 ± 4.47	0.7348	10	1232.14 ± 6 ± 11.83	0.9597
2	7.5	888.222 ± 6.78	0.7633	15	1809.66 ± 6 ± 11.22	0.6234
3	10	1196.970 ± 9.06	0.7574	20	2389.26 ± 8 ± 7.49	0.3138
4	12.5	1511.508 ± 11.83	0.7829	25	3049.42 ± 2 ± 10.99	0.3601
5	15	1771.398 ± 16.33	0.9218	30	3561.77 ± 3 ± 16.06	0.4509

*= average of three determinations, RSD=Relative standard deviation

Table 4: Recovery data for NEB and CIL by HPLC method.

Drug	Accuracy Level %	Amount taken (µg/ml)	Amount added (µg/ml)	Total Amount found * (µg/ml)	% Recovery ± SD
NEB	80%	5	4	9.010	100.108 ± 0.993
	100%	5	5	9.954	99.711 ± 0.651
	120%	5	6	10.983	99.698 ± 0.489
CIL	80%	10	8	17.898	99.497 ± 0.673
	100%	10	10	19.972	99.512 ± 0.465
	120%	10	12	21.904	99.510 ± 0.278

*= average of three determinations

Table 5: Precision study for NEB and CIL.

Parameters	Conc.		% RSD	
	NEB (µg/ml)	CIL (µg/ml)	NEB	CIL
Intra-day* precision	5	10	0.640	0.490
	10	20	0.452	1.084
	15	30	0.715	0.871
Inter-day* precision	5	10	1.020	0.304
	10	20	0.521	0.374
	15	30	0.389	0.802
Repeatability**	10	20	0.541	0.621

*= average of three determinations,

**= average of six determinations

Table 6: Robustness.

Parameter	Change Level	Peak Area	
		NEB	CIL
pH (±0.2)	4.8	1238.068	2532.057
	5.0#	1256.126	2512.223
	5.2	1266.059	2437.762
	Mean ± SD	1253.418 ± 14.1968	2494.014 ± 49.71481
	%RSD	1.13	1.68
Detection wavelength (± 2.0 nm)	223	1260.910	2564.526
	225#	1256.126	2512.223
	227	1274.839	2584.222
	Mean ± SD	1263.958 ± 9.722	2553.657 ± 37.20975
	%RSD	0.769	1.45
Mobile phase Composition (±2.0 ml)	28:72	1245.220	2537.143
	30:70#	1256.126	2512.223
	32:68	1263.519	2556.829
	Mean ± SD	1254.955 ± 9.20553	2535.398 ± 22.35412
	%RSD	0.734	0.882

#= actual parameter as control standard

Figure 4: Calibration curve of neбиволol HCl (5-15 µg/ml).

Figure 5: Calibration curve of cilnidipine (10-30 µg/ml).

Table 7: Analysis on marketed formulation.

Nebivolol HCl			Cilnidipine		
Labelled amount (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Assay	Labelled amount (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Assay
5 mg	5.057	101.14	10mg	9.913	99.13
	5.114	102.28		9.816	98.16
	5.108	102.16		9.878	98.78
Mean ± SD	5.093 ± 0.031	101.863 ± 0.627	Mean ± SD	9.869 ± 0.049	99.69 ± 0.490
%RSD	0.641	0.615	%RSD	0.497	0.496

Conclusions

Results for validation parameters are in good agreement with label claim, which indicates that there is no interference of excipients in routinely used experiment. The proposed method is found to be accurate and precise, therefore proposed method can be used for routine analysis of Nebivolol HCl and Cilnidipine in tablet dosage form.

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References

- Rang and Dale's Pharmacology, 6th Edition, Churchill Livingstone Publishers (P) Ltd, New York; 2004: 277-285.
- Drug profile for Nebivolol. Available from: <http://www.drugbank.ca/drugs/DB04861>. Accessed 15 March 2016.
- Drug profile for Nebivolol. Available from: <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nebivolol>. Accessed 15 March 2016.
- Parambi GT, Mathew M, Jose A, Revikumar KG. A validated U.V. spectrophotometric determination of an antihypertensive drug – Nebivolol from tablet formulations. *Int J Pharm Sci Review Res.* 2010;139:141-3.
- Haripriya SN, Bhavani SN, Satyanarayana M, Anumolu PD. Simultaneous quantification of nebivolol hydrochloride and hydrochlorothiazide by first derivative UV- Spectroscopy. *Der Pharm. letter.* 2013;78:84-5.
- Chetan MB, Hanumanthachar KJ, Jayanthi C. RP-HPLC estimation of Nebivolol. *Int J Pharm Bio Sci.* 2012;1594:1596-3.
- Sahoo MK, Giri RK, Barik CS, Kanungo SK. RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Nebivolol in tablet dosage form. *E J Chem.* 2009;915:919-6.
- Sharma A, Patel B, Patel R. Simultaneous estimation of Nebivolol Hydrochloride and Samlodipine Besylate by High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography. *Int J Pharm Bio Sci.* 2010;339:347-1.
- Vyas HR, Patel SS, Ladva BJ, Nayak BS, Patel SJ, Mahida VM. Development of stability-indicating HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Nebivolol Hydrochloride and Valsartan in tablet dosage form. *World J Pharm and Pharm Sci.* 2015;662:670-4.
- Dangi M, Chaudhry D, Sinker M, Racha V. Stability indicating HPTLC method for estimation of Nebivolol Hydrochloride and

- Amlodipine Besylate in combination. Eurasian J Anal Chem. 2010;161:169-5.
11. Drug profile for Cilnidipine. Available from: <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cilnidipine>. Accessed 15 March 2016.
 12. Drug profile for Cilnidipine. Available from: www.drugbank.ca/drugs/DB03614. Accessed 15 March 2016.
 13. Mohammed M. Spectrophotometric method for the estimation of Cilnidipine in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. Orient J Chem. 2013;131:134-29.
 14. Lee KR, Chae YJ, Lee JH, Kim DD, Chong S, Shim CK, et al. Quantification of Cilnidipine in human plasma by Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry. J Liq Chroma-to & Related Tech. 2012;308:20-35.
 15. Zhang X, Zhai S, Zhao R, Ouyang J, Li X, Baeyens WR. Determination of Cilnidipine, a new calcium antagonist, in human plasma using High Performance Liquid Chromatography with tandem Mass Spectrometric detection. Anal Chim Acta. 2007;142:146-1.
 16. Soni V, Kakadiya J, Patel P, Shah N. Development and Validation of High Performance Thin Layer Chromatographic method for Cilnidipine and Metoprolol Succinate in their combined pharmaceutical dosage form. Int J Pharma Nano Sci. 2014;61:72-3.